

RES differences between MELiSsa.2018.01 and the previous version (MELiSsa.2015.6)

- Residential heating system (slide 2-3)
- Insulation measures (slide 4)

RESIDENTIAL HEATING SYSTEMS (MELiSsa.2015.6), :

In MELiSsa.2018.01, technologies highlighted in red are removed and those highlighted in yellow are modified (see next slide)

RESIDENTIAL HEATING SYSTEMS (MELiSsa.2018.01):

Technologies highlighted in yellow are modified compared to the previous version - some of them now provide only space heating («s») and some of them now provide also hot water («2° mode»). The four technologies highlighted in green are newly added. Moreover, two clusters have been set (C and I)

INSULATION MEASURES IN RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS (MELiSsa.2018.01). Red parts already existed in the previous version (MELiSsa.2015.6)

